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Termodinamik masalalarni yechish

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Qo‘qon DPI “Fizika va astronomiya” kafedrasi o‘qituvchisi

Аннотация Ushbu maqolada umumiy fizika kursining termodinamika bo‘limini o‘qitishda, tizim entropiyasi o‘zgarishini aniqlash qismida talabalar ancha qiyinchiliklarga uchrashadi, chunki ular fizik jarayonlardagi umumiy tushuncha va xulosalarni xususiy hollarga to‘liq va aniq tadbiq qilishga qiynalishadi. Bu ishning asosiy maqsadi talabalarga amaliy mashg‘ulotlarda tizim entropiyasi o‘zgarishini aniqlashda metodik yordam ko‘rsatishdan iborat.

Kalitli so‘zlar: termodinamika, tizim entropiyasi o‘zgarishi, entropiya-sistemi, qaytuvchan jarayon, izobarik jarayon, izotermik jarayon, izoxorik jarayon, adiabatik jarayon

Umumiy fizika kursining termodinamika bo‘limini o‘qitishda, ayniqsa, tizim entropiyasi o‘zgarishini aniqlash qismida talabalar ancha qiyinchiliklarga uchrashadi, chunki ular fizik jarayonlardagi umumiy tushuncha va xulosalarni xususiy hollarga to‘liq va aniq tadbiq qilishga qiynalishadi. Shu sababli, bu ishning asosiy maqsadi talabalarga amaliy mashg‘ulotlarda tizim entropiyasi o‘zgarishini aniqlashda metodik yordam ko‘rsatishdan iborat. Bizga ma‘lumki, qaytuvchan jarayonlar uchun tizim entropiyasining elementar o‘zgarishi quydagiga teng [1]:

$$dS = \frac{dQ}{T}, \quad (1)$$

Bu yerda dQ -tizimga berilgan (olingan) elementar issiqlik miqdori, T -isitkichning (sovitkichning) harorati. Demak, entropiya-sistema holatining shunday funksiyasiki, bu funktsiyaning qaytuvchan jarayondagi cheksiz kichik o‘zgarishi (dS) mazkur jarayonda kiritilgan cheksiz kichik issiqlik miqdorining (dQ) shu issiqlik kiritilayotgan holatdagi sistema absolyut temperaturasiga (T) nisbati bilan aniqlanadi.

Tizim termodinamik jarayon natijasida boshlang‘ich “1” holatdan oxirgi “2” holatga o‘tsin, u holda (1) ifodani integrallasak:

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$$\int_{S_1}^{S_2} dS = \int_1^2 \frac{dQ}{T} \text{ yoki } \Delta S = S_2 - S_1 = \int_1^2 \frac{dQ}{T}, \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda ΔS -entropiya o'zgarishi, S_1 va S_2 tizimning boshlang'ich va ohirgi holatlaridagi entropiyasi. Qaytuvchan jarayon uchun $\Delta S = 0$ ($S_1 = S_2$) va qaytmas jarayon uchun esa $\Delta S > 0$ ($S_2 > S_1$) ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi. Demak, berk (izolyatsiyalangan) tizimda qaytuvchan jarayon amalga oshganda entropiya o'zgarmaydi, qaytmas jarayon sodir bo'lganda esa entropiya ortadi. Shu sababli izolyatsiyalangan tizimdagi tabiiy jarayonlar entropiyasi ortadigan yo'nalishda amalga oshadi.

Tizim entropiyasi o'zgarishini aniqlashdan oldin Mendeleyev-Klayperon tenglamasi (MKT) va termodinamika 1-qonunining diferensial ko'rinishini esga olaylik:

$$pV = \nu RT \quad (3) \text{ va } dQ = dU + dA = dU + pdV, \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $dU = \frac{i}{2} \nu R dT$ -tizim ichki entropiyasining o'zgarishi, $dA = pdV$ -tizimning elementar bajargan ishi.

Demak, tizimga berilgan (olingan) elementar issiqlik miqdori:

$$dQ = \frac{i}{2} \nu RT + pdV \quad (5)$$

gazlar uchun tizim entropiyasi o'zgarishini aniqlash usullarini ko'rib chiqaylik:

1. Izotermik jarayonda ($T = const$) $T = 0$, shu sababli $dU = 0$ bo'ladi, natijada (4) dan $dQ = dA = pdV$. MKT dan $p = \nu RT/V$, oxirgi ikkita ifodani (2) ga qo'ysak:

$$\Delta S = \int_1^2 \frac{dQ}{T} = \int_1^2 \frac{pdV}{T} = \int_1^2 \frac{\nu RT dV}{V} = \nu R \int_{V_1}^{V_2} \frac{dV}{V} = \nu R \ln \frac{V_2}{V_1} \quad (6)$$

2. Izobarik jarayonda ($p = const$) $dp = 0$. MKTni diferensiallasak $pdV = \nu R dT$, buni (5) ga qo'ysak:

$$dQ = \frac{i}{2} \nu R dT + \nu R dT = \frac{i+2}{2} \nu R dT, \text{ natijada:}$$

$$\Delta S = \int_1^2 \frac{dQ}{T} = \frac{i+2}{2} \nu R \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \frac{dT}{T} = \frac{i+2}{2} \nu R \ln \frac{T_2}{T_1}. \quad (7)$$

$$\text{yoki } \frac{T_2}{T_1} = \frac{V_2}{V_1} \text{ dan: } \Delta S = \frac{i+2}{2} \nu R \ln \frac{V_2}{V_1}. \quad (8)$$

3. Izoxorik jarayonda ($V=const$) $dV=0$ va $dA = pdV = 0$, natijada

$$dQ = dU = \frac{i}{2} \nu R dT \text{ va } \Delta S = \frac{i}{2} \nu R \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \frac{dT}{T} = \frac{i}{2} \nu R \ln \frac{T_2}{T_1} \quad (9)$$

4. Adiabatik jarayonda $dQ=0$, shu sababli: $\Delta S = \int_1^2 \frac{dQ}{T} = 0$. Demak, bu jarayonda tizim entropiyasi o'zgarmaydi.

Suyuqlik va qattiq jismlar qizitilganda yoki sovutilgandagi entropiya o'zgarishi:

$$\Delta S = \int_1^2 \frac{dQ}{T} = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} \frac{c m dT}{T} = c m \ln \frac{T_2}{T_1}, \quad (10)$$

bu yerda c va m -jism solishtirma issiqlik sig'imi va massasi. Suyuqlik bug'langanda esa ($T=\text{const}$) entropiya o'zgarishi:

$$\Delta S = \int_1^2 \frac{dQ}{T} = \frac{1}{T} \int_1^2 dQ = \frac{Q_b}{T} = \frac{\lambda m}{T}, \quad (11)$$

bu yerda λ -suyuqlikni solishtirma bug'lanish issiqligi. Bu formulalar yordamida talabalar berilgan masalalarni aniq va to'g'ri yechishlari mumkin.

Misol tariqasida bir nechta masalalarini ko'rib chiqaylik [2]:

1-masala. Massasi $m=10$ gramm kislorod izotermik kengayganda hajmi $V_1=25$ litrdan $V_2=100$ litrgacha o'zgarsa, uning entropiyasi qanchalik o'zgarganligi aniqlansin.

Berilgan:

$$O_2; \quad \mu = 32 * 10^{-3} \text{ kg/mol}, \quad m=10 \text{ gr}=10^{-2} \text{ kg}; \quad V_1=25 \text{ l}=25 * 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3; \\ V_2=100 \text{ l}=0,1 \text{ m}^3$$

Topish kerak: $\Delta S = S_2 - S_1 = ?$

Masala yechimi. Izotermik jarayonda tizim entropiyasi o'zgarishini aniqlash uchun (6) formuladan foydalanamiz:

$$\Delta S = \nu R \ln \frac{V_2}{V_1} = \frac{m}{\mu} R \ln \frac{V_2}{V_1} \text{ yoki}$$

$$\Delta S = \left(10^{-2} / 32 * 10^{-3} \right) * 8,31 * \ln(0,1 / 25 * 10^{-3}) = 3,6 \text{ J/K}$$

2-masala. Massasi $m=0,1$ kg suv $t_1=0^\circ\text{C}$ dan to $t_2=100^\circ\text{C}$ gacha qizdirilib, so'ngra shu haroratda to'liq bug'ga aylantirilsa, tizim entropiyasi qanchalik o'zgarganligini aniqlansin.

Berilgan: H_2O ; $m=0,1$ kg; $c = 4200 \text{ J/kg} * K$ -suvning solishtirma issiqlik sig'imi; $\lambda = 2,3 * 10^6 \text{ J/K}$ -bug'lanish solishtirma issiqligi; $T_1=t_1+273^\circ\text{C}$, $T_2=373^\circ\text{K}$

Topish kerak: $\Delta S = \Delta S_1 + \Delta S_2 = ?$ bu yerda ΔS_1 va ΔS_2 -mos ravishda suvning qizdirishdagi va bug'ga aylantirishdagi entropiya o'zgarishi.

Masala yechimi. Suyuqlik qizitilganda uning entropiyasi o'zgarishi (10) formuladan aniqlanadi:

$$\Delta S_1 = c m \ln \left(\frac{T_2}{T_1} \right) = 4200 * 0,1 * \ln \left(\frac{373}{273} \right) = 132 \text{ J/K}$$

Suyuqlik (suv) bug'langanda esa uning entropiyasi o'zgarishi (11) formuladan topiladi:

$$\Delta S_2 = \frac{\lambda m}{T_2} = \frac{2,3 * 10^6 * 0,1}{373} = 617 \text{ J/K}$$

Natijada, tizim entropiyasining to'liq o'zgarishi:

$$\Delta S = \Delta S_1 + \Delta S_2 = 132 + 617 = 749 \text{ J/K}$$

3-masala. Massasi $m_1=5\text{kg}$ va harorati $T_1=280^\circ\text{C}$ bo'lgan suv massasi $m_2=8\text{kg}$ va harorati $T_2=350^\circ\text{C}$ bo'lgan suv bilan aralashtirilsa, natijaviy harorat θ va entropiya o'zgarishi ΔS aniqlansin.

Berilgan: $m_1=5\text{kg}$; $T_1=280^\circ\text{C}$; $m_2=8\text{kg}$; $T_2=350^\circ\text{C}$; $c=4200\text{J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$

Topish kerak: $\theta=?$ va $\Delta S = \Delta S_1 + \Delta S_2 = ?$, bu yerda ΔS_1 va ΔS_2 -mos ravishda m_1 va m_2 massali suvlarning isishi va sovushdagi entropiyalarining o'zgarishi.

Masala yechimi. Aralashmaning natijaviy θ haroratini issiqlik balans tenglamasidan topamiz.

$\sum Q(\text{olingan}) = \sum Q(\text{berilgan})$ bu yerda $Q = cm\Delta T$ - issiqlik miqdori.

Masala uchun $Q(\text{olingan}) = cm_1(\theta - T_1) = cm_1\theta - cm_1\Delta T$ va

$Q(\text{bergan}) = cm_2(T_2 - \theta) = cm_2T_2 - cm_2\theta$, bularni issiqlik balans tenglamasiga qo'yib, natijaviy haroratni aniqlaymiz:

$$\theta = \frac{T_1 m_1 + m_2 T_2}{m_1 + m_2} = \frac{5 \cdot 280 + 8 \cdot 350}{5 + 8} = 323^\circ\text{K}$$

Massalari m_1 va m_2 bo'lgan suvlarning entropiyasi o'zgarishi (10) formuladan mos ravishda aniqlanadi.

$$\Delta S_1 = cm_1 \ln \frac{\theta}{T_1} \text{ va } \Delta S_2 = cm_2 \ln \frac{\theta}{T_2}$$

Tizim entropiyasining o'zgarishi esa:

$$\Delta S = \Delta S_1 + \Delta S_2 = c(m_1 \ln \frac{\theta}{T_1} + m_2 \ln \frac{\theta}{T_2}) = 4200(5 * \ln \frac{323}{280} + 8 \ln \frac{323}{350}) = 300 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{K}}$$

4-masala. Massasi $m=4\text{g}$ azot gazi $V_1=5\text{l}$ dan to $V_2=9\text{l}$ hajmga izobarik kengaysa, uning entropiyasi o'zgarishi aniqlansin.

Berilgan: N_2 ; $i=5$ -azot molekulasining erkinlik darajasi; $\mu = 28 * 10^{-3} \text{ kg/mol}$; $p=\text{const}$; $m=4 * 10^{-3} \text{ kg}$; $V_1=5\text{l}$; $V_2=9\text{l}$.

Topish kerak: $\Delta S = ?$

Masala yechimi: Izobarik jarayonda tizim entropiyasi o'zgarishini aniqlash uchun (8) formuladan foydalanamiz:

$$\Delta S = \frac{i + 2}{2} * \frac{m}{\mu} R \ln \frac{V_2}{V_1} = \frac{5 + 2}{2} * \frac{4 * 10^{-3}}{28 * 10^{-3}} 8,31 \ln \frac{9}{5} = 2,43 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{K}}$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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